

РАЗДЕЛ. МЕДИЦИНСКИЕ НАУКИ

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**МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОСТОЯНИЯ
ФЕТОПЛАЦЕНТАРНОГО КОМПЛЕКСА У ЖЕНЩИН С
ВНУТРИУТРОБНОЙ ГИПОКСИЕЙ ПЛОДА**

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Аннотация: Проведено исследование с участием 55 беременных женщин и морфологическое исследование 12 плацент пациенток, с установленным в условиях стационара диагнозом внутриутробная гипоксия плода. Выявлены основные морфофункциональные изменения, происходящие в плаценте при формировании внутриутробной гипоксии плода. При макроскопическом исследовании плацент был диагностирован сниженный плацентарно-плодный коэффициент. Напряжение компенсаторно-приспособительных реакций подтверждается наличием синцитио-капиллярных мембран, синцитио-капиллярных почеч, разрастание материнского фибриноида.

Ключевые слова: плацента, морфологические изменения, внутриутробная гипоксия плода

**MORPHOFUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF THE STATE OF THE
FETOPLACENTAL COMPLEX IN WOMEN WITH INTRAUTERINE
FETAL HYPOXIA**

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Annotation: A study was conducted with the participation of 55 pregnant women and a morphological study of 12 placentas of patients with a diagnosis of intrauterine fetal hypoxia established in a hospital setting. The main morphofunctional changes in the placenta during the formation of intrauterine fetal hypoxia were revealed. A macroscopic examination of the placenta was diagnosed with a reduced placental-fetal ratio. The tension of compensatory-adaptive reactions is confirmed by the presence of syncytio-capillary membranes, syncytio-capillary kidneys, proliferation of maternal fibrinoid.

Keywords: placenta, morphological changes, intrauterine fetal hypoxia

Relevance. Fetal Fetal hypoxia is an intrauterine syndrome characterized by a complex of changes on the part of the fetus due to insufficient oxygen supply to its tissues and organs. Fetal hypoxia is characterized by disorders of the vital organs, primarily the central nervous system [5].

According to the literature, intrauterine fetal hypoxia in 46.7-86% of cases becomes the main cause of perinatal mortality and disability in newborns. Statistical studies conducted over the past ten years indicate an upward trend in this pathology among children, which is directly related to the changes occurring in the "mother-placenta-fetus" system [1, 3]. Fetal hypoxia can develop at different periods of intrauterine development, characterized by varying degrees of oxygen deficiency and consequences for the child's body. Fetal hypoxia, which develops in the early stages of gestation, causes defects and a slowdown in the development of the embryo. In late pregnancy, hypoxia is accompanied by fetal growth retardation, damage to the central nervous system, and a decrease in the adaptive capacity of the newborn [6, 7].

Intrauterine fetal hypoxia can be a consequence of a wide range of adverse processes occurring in the body of the child, mother, or in the placenta. The probability of developing hypoxia in the fetus increases with diseases of the maternal body – anemia, cardiovascular pathology, kidney disease, respiratory system, diabetes mellitus [4].

The risk of fetal hypoxia increases with violations of the fetal-placental circulation caused by the threat of miscarriage, prolonged pregnancy, umbilical cord pathology, placental insufficiency and other complications of pregnancy. Risk factors in the development of intrapartum hypoxia include hemolytic disease of the fetus, congenital malformations, intrauterine infection, repeated and tight entanglement of the umbilical cord around the baby's neck [2, 8].

In response to fetal hypoxia, the nervous system suffers first of all, since the nervous tissue is most sensitive to oxygen deficiency. Starting from 6-11 weeks of embryo development, a lack of oxygen causes a delay in the maturation of the

brain, disturbances in the structure and functioning of blood vessels, and a slowdown in the maturation of the blood-brain barrier. Also, hypoxia is experienced by the tissues of the kidneys, heart, and intestines of the fetus [6].

The aim of the study – was to study the morphological and functional features of the state of the fetoplacental complex in women with intrauterine fetal hypoxia.

Materials and methods. 55 birth histories and neonatal histories were analyzed, as well as 12 placentas from women diagnosed with intrauterine fetal hypoxia in a hospital setting. Their birth histories and neonatal histories were analyzed: group 1 consisted of 38 women with pregnancies complicated by intrauterine fetal hypoxia; group 2 consisted of 17 women with a favorable pregnancy.

Results of the study. The average age of patients in the first group was 21.7 ± 0.09 years, in the second group – 24.5 ± 0.09 . A burdened somatic history in the first group had 17 women (44.7 %), in the second group – 5 (29.4 %). A burdened obstetric and gynecological anamnesis was found in 25 (65.8%) and 1 (5.9 %), respectively.

Among the complications of pregnancy, the threat of termination of pregnancy in group 1 was noted in 76.7 % of cases, and intrauterine infection of the fetus – in 53.1%. In group 2, all complications did not exceed 22 %. In group 1, in 47.7 % of cases, pregnancy ended in preterm labor, and in group 2, term delivery was the main outcome (85 %).

Diagnosis of fetal hypoxia was based on data from the biophysical profile of the fetus, cardiocography, dopplerometry of the uteroplacental circulation, ultrasound fetometry. Among the pathological conditions of newborns, in addition to intrauterine fetal hypoxia, in group 1, prematurity, intrauterine infection and cerebral ischemia were the leading ones. In group 2, pathological conditions such as intrauterine hypoxia and fetal malnutrition were not found.

Analysis of placenta samples showed that the average weight of the placentas was 485 ± 0.25 grams, the diameter of terminal villi was 31.2 ± 1.1 μm . Microscopically, the following picture was revealed: the prevalence of mature-type villi, in which an uneven deficiency of terminal branches is noted – 100 %; focal deposits of maternal fibrinoid – 68 %; the marginal location of the umbilical cord – 42 %; foci of calcification – 53 %.

Bacteriological cultures with afterbirth revealed opportunistic and pathogenic flora. Representatives of E.Coli prevailed – 54.4 %, Acinetobacter – 32.2 %, Enterobacter – 21.7 %, Streptococcus faecalis – 19.3 %, Staphylococcus epidermidis – 17.4 %, Staphylococcus aureus – 29.1 %, Candida and Klebsiela – 10.2 % and 13.1 %, respectively, and other microorganisms accounted for 12.0 %. The presence of microbial seeding of the placenta leads to pronounced morphological changes in the uterine-placental-fetal complex, and causes

irreversible disturbances in the adaptive functions of this complex, which has a negative effect on the course of pregnancy and perinatal outcomes.

As a result of the pathomorphological examination of the placentas, it was revealed that the histological basis is involutive-dystrophic and compensatory-adaptive reactions in the placenta, a violation of the maturation of chorionic villi, and inflammatory changes in the placenta. With changes in the structure of the placenta caused by pathology in the mother's body, the existing compensatory reactions increase and new ones arise, which ensures a sufficiently high functional activity for a certain period, and as a consequence, the maintenance of a satisfactory life of the fetus.

Conclusions. The main pregnancy outcome in group 1 was premature birth (47.7 %), and in group 2 – term delivery (85 %). The most common complications of pregnancy in group 1 were the threat of termination of pregnancy (76.7 %) and intrauterine infection of the fetus (53.1 %). Among the pathological conditions of newborns, in addition to intrauterine fetal hypoxia, in group 1, prematurity, intrauterine infection and cerebral ischemia were the leading ones. In a macroscopic examination of the placenta, there is a reduced placental-fetal ratio in group 1. Whereas, in group 2, the placental-fetal ratio was statistically significantly increased. The presence of syncytio-capillary membranes, syncytio-capillary kidneys, and the proliferation of maternal fibrinoid testify in favor of the tension of compensatory-adaptive reactions.

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